

WORLD CONGRESS
ON OSTEOPOROSIS,
OSTEOARTHRITIS AND
MUSCULOSKELETAL
DISEASES

AbstractBook

WCO
IOF-ESCEO

2025 ROME

April 10-13, 2025

Roma Convention Center
La Nuvola **Rome | Italy**

WORLD'S LEADING CLINICAL CONFERENCE
ON BONE, JOINT AND MUSCLE HEALTH

Congress Organizer Sinklar Congress Management B.V.

Congress Secretariat www.humacom.com

www.WCO-IOF-ESCEO.org

EVENT

WCO-IOF-ESCEO**April 10-13, 2025**

WORLD CONGRESS ON OSTEOPOROSIS, OSTEOARTHRITIS AND MUSCULOSKELETAL DISEASES

CONGRESS CHAIRMEN

Jean-Yves REGINSTER

ESCEO President

John A. KANIS

IOF Honorary President

PROGRAMME COMMITTEE

Nicholas C. Harvey

IOF President

René RIZZOLI

Chair, ESCEO Scientific Advisory Board (SAB)

Cyrus COOPER

IOF Honorary President

John A. KANIS

IOF Honorary President

Jean-Yves REGINSTER

ESCEO President

SCIENTIFIC ADVISORY BOARD
AND ABSTRACTS REVIEWERS

J. BAUER

I. BAUTMANS

C. BEAUDART

E. BIVER

A. BORG

M. L. BRANDI

O. BRUYÈRE

F. BUCKINX

N. BURLET

E. CAVALIER

M. CESARI

R. CHAPURLAT

A. CHERUBINI

T. CHEVALLEY

C. COOPER

B. CORTET

A. CRUZ-JENTOFT

B. DAWSON-HUGHES

E. DENNISON

J.-P. DEVOGELAER

A. DIEZ-PEREZ

H. P. DIMAI

F. DINCER

R. FIELDING

N. FUGGLE

A. GASPARIK

E. GIELEN

N. C. HARVEY

M. HILIGSMANN

J. A. KANIS

J.-M. KAUFMAN

J.-F. KAUX

A. KURTH

F. LANDI

A. LASLOP

S. MAGGI

J. MARTEL-PELLETIER

R. MATIJEVIC

A. MOBASHERI

J. PACCOU

J.-P. PELLETIER

D. PINTO

D. PRIETO-ALHAMBRA

F. RANNOU

J.-Y. REGINSTER

R. RIZZOLI

Y. ROLLAND

S. SABICO

C. SIEBER

P. SZULC

T. THOMAS

F. THOMASIUŠ

A. TROMBETTI

Ş. TÜZÜN

B. VELLAS

N. VERONESE

P740

BERTOLOTTI SYNDROME – HIDDEN CAUSE OF LOWER BACK PAINS. Delezan¹, L. J. Drazic², K. Boskovic¹, J. Zvekić - Svorcan¹, T. Tasic¹, N. Bastaja¹, T. Bjeletic¹¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine Novi Sad. Special Hospital for Rheumatic Diseases, Novi Sad, Serbia, ²Special Hospital for Rheumatic Diseases, Novi Sad, Serbia

Objectives: Differential radiological evaluation in a female patient with lower back pain syndrome (LBPS) with a focus on Bertolotti syndrome (BS). BS is characterized by the presence of a lumbosacral transitional vertebra, in the form of an enlarged transverse process of the fifth lumbar vertebra (greater than 19 mm), with a tendency toward pseudoarticulation or fusion with the sacrum, with or without compromise of the nerve roots. Based on the presence of pseudoarthrosis, BS is classified into four groups according to the Castellvi classification, with two subgroups: A (unilateral) and B (bilateral).

Material and Methods: A 76-year-old female patient presents with chronic pain in the hips and lower back. Radiographs of the pelvis in the AP lying position were performed on a Philips DuraDiagnostic F30 machine. Ethical approval (No. 14/01-2/1-25, 13.01.2025.) was obtained from the ethics committee of the Special Hospital for Rheumatic Diseases in Novi Sad, Serbia, and the patient signed an informed consent form.

Results: An oval bony formation, approximately 30 mm in size, is positioned para-vertebral and suprasacral on the left side of the fifth lumbar vertebral body. This formation could belong to the transverse process of the fifth lumbar vertebra or an extension of the lateral side of the first sacral vertebra. The above-described findings may indicate Bertolotti syndrome type IIIa, according to the Castellvi classification, based on the absence of pseudoarthrosis.

Conclusion: The pelvic X-ray raises suspicion of Bertolotti syndrome. The patient has been referred for a CT scan of the lumbar spine to confirm the definitive diagnosis.

P741

GLUCOCORTICOID - INDUCED OSTEOPOROSIS IN A PATIENT WITH SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME – CASE REPORTS. Delezan¹, S. Mandić², K. Bjelić³, B. Erdeljan⁴, J. Zvekić - Svorcan¹, T. Janković¹, K. Bosković¹¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine Novi Sad. Special Hospital for Rheumatic Diseases, Novi Sad, Serbia, ²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine Novi Sad. Institute for Pulmonary Diseases of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia, ³University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine Novi Sad. Health Center Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia, ⁴Special Hospital for Rheumatic Diseases, Novi Sad, Serbia

Objective: Case report of a patient suffering from Sjögren's syndrome (SS) with iatrogenic osteoporosis and multiple fractures caused by glucocorticoids (GCs).

Material and Methods: A 62-year-old female patient was hospitalized at the Special Hospital for Rheumatic Diseases in Novi Sad due to osteoporosis and multiple fractures. Clinical, radiological (DXA), basic laboratory and bone metabolism marker tests were performed. Ethical approval (No. 14/02-1/1-25, 27.01.2025.) was obtained from the ethics committee of the Special Hospital for Rheumatic Diseases in Novi Sad, Serbia, and the patient signed an informed consent form.

Results: The first symptoms, including dryness of the eyes and mouth, difficulty swallowing, joint pain, and swelling of the neck lymph nodes, appeared in 2003. This coincided with laboratory confirmation of leukopenia and anemia, and the diagnosis of primary SS was made. Glucocorticoid therapy was initiated. In 2010, the patient's symptoms worsened, presenting as acute polyarthritis with morning stiffness. Antimalarials and GCs were introduced into the treatment regimen. Due to inadequate clinical response, methotrexate was added to the therapy but was soon discontinued due to leukopenia and anemia. Treatment continued with antimalarials and GCs. In 2019, an attempt to discontinue GC therapy led to an exacerbation of symptoms. Due to anemia, a pathohistological examination of a bone marrow biopsy was performed, which revealed hypoplastic changes and osteoporosis. In late 2013, after a fall, the patient sustained pathological fractures of Th6 and Th7 vertebrae. In 2019, a fracture occurred at Th12 vertebra, followed by a fracture of the fourth finger of the right hand in 2020, and a fracture of L3 vertebra in 2024. Recent laboratory results for bone markers show moderate activity of bone structure breakdown, while the DXA scan suggests osteopenia. The ESSDAI score is 20 and the ESSPRI score is 8.33. Despite prolonged use of antimalarials and GCs, adequate disease control has not been achieved. In November 2024, sulfasalazine was replaced with azathioprine.

Conclusion: Although an attempt was made to de-escalate GC therapy due to osteoporosis, there are currently no effective therapeutic options. The patient will be reevaluated for more modern treatments for osteoporosis and SS.